

Corporate Governance, Sustainability, and Corporate Performance: Multi-Level Perspectives from Existing Companies

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Abstract

This article explores the complex relationship between corporate governance (GCG), sustainability, and firm performance, focusing on incumbent firms in the plastic packaging industry. It adopts a multi-level perspective, examining how factors at the individual (e.g., entrepreneurial orientation), organizational (e.g., board structure), and ecosystem (e.g., stakeholder engagement) levels interact to shape sustainability performance. The article delves into the dynamics of proactive versus reactive approaches in firms' sustainability transitions, emphasizing the critical role of circular business model innovation in achieving sustainability goals. By analyzing in-depth case studies and empirical evidence from diverse contexts, this article aims to provide insights into how incumbent firms can successfully navigate the challenges and opportunities associated with sustainability, contributing to the development of more environmentally and socially responsible business models.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Sustainability, Kinerja Perusahaan, CSR, Sustainability Disclosure, Circular Business Model.

1. Introduction

Corporate Governance (CG) has garnered increasing attention, particularly due to the growing demand for transparency and accountability in business practices (Aras & Crowther, 2008; Diamastuti et al., 2021). CG encompasses a set of mechanisms, both internal (e.g., managerial ownership, board of directors) and external (e.g., institutional ownership), designed to align the interests of management with those of shareholders and other stakeholders. Prior research has indicated that effective CG can enhance financial performance, mitigate risks, and boost investor confidence (Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu George, 2007).

Alongside CG, the concept of sustainability has also gained prominence. Corporate sustainability involves managing the environmental and social impacts of business operations, in addition to financial performance (Jamali et al., 2008). Incumbent firms, in particular, face unique challenges in integrating sustainability practices into their established business models (Zucchella et al., 2022). This article aims to address a gap in the existing literature by investigating the complex relationship between corporate governance, sustainability, and firm performance from a multi-level perspective, with a specific focus on incumbent firms in the plastic packaging industry (Chabachib et al., 2020). The discussion examines how factors at the individual (e.g., entrepreneurial orientation), organizational (e.g., board structure), and ecosystem (e.g., stakeholder engagement) levels interact to shape sustainability performance. Furthermore, it explores the dynamics of proactive versus reactive approaches in firms' sustainability transitions (Zucchella et al., 2022), as well as the crucial role of circular business model innovation in achieving sustainability goals.

The following table summarizes a comparison of research findings and article weaknesses from various studies that examine aspects of corporate governance (CG), corporate social responsibility (CSR), and firm performance in different contexts. This table aims to provide a clearer picture of the main findings and limitations of each article, as well as highlight the relevance and scope of the research across various industries and countries.

Table 1. Comparison of Research Findings and Article Weaknesses on Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility

Author	Research Findings	Article Weaknesses
Barbu & Bocean (2007)	This article shows that good corporate governance (GCG) is positively correlated with company performance.	This article focuses only on companies in developed countries, so the relevance of its findings to developing countries is questionable. The research is also limited to quantitative data and does not delve deeper into how GCG is implemented in different contexts.
Chabachib et al. (2020)	This article shows that managerial ownership, the proportion of independent commissioners, and board size positively affect company performance, while institutional ownership negatively affects it.	The research is limited to non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018, so it cannot be generalized to all companies. The article also does not account for other factors outside GCG that may affect company performance.
Yahaya & Musa, (2023)	This article examines the role of corporate governance in maximizing company value in 134 companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The findings show that risk committee size, leverage, tangible assets, profitability, and company size have significant effects on company value.	The research is limited to the sample size and companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Further research is expected to include all 156 companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange and add other corporate governance characteristics that have been proven to be influential.
Jamali et al. (2008)	This article explores the reciprocal relationship between corporate governance (GCG) and corporate social responsibility (CSR) in Lebanon. The research finds that good GCG is considered an essential pillar for sustainable CSR.	The research is limited to one country and a small sample size (eight companies), so the results may not be widely generalizable. The evidence collected is also based on self-reporting, which raises the possibility of bias.

Author	Research Findings	Article Weaknesses
Aras & Crowther (2008)	This article investigates the relationship between corporate governance and sustainability in FTSE100 companies. The research finds several strengths and weaknesses in corporate governance practices related to sustainability.	The research is limited to FTSE100 companies and is primarily qualitative. Further research is needed to analyze sectoral differences in approaches to corporate governance practices.
Diamastuti et al. (2021)	This article examines the direct and indirect effects of government roles, organizational commitment, and media exposure on corporate social and environmental responsibility disclosure (CSERD) in 42 state-owned enterprises (SOEs) in Indonesia. The results show that government roles and organizational commitment have a direct influence on GCG and CSERD.	The research is limited to SOEs in Indonesia and does not consider private companies. Additionally, the study focuses only on CSER disclosure, not on the actual implementation of CSR practices.
Zucchella et al. (2021)	This article discusses the transition to a circular business model in existing entrepreneurial companies in the plastic packaging industry. The findings show that the challenges of circularity create dilemmas on how to interpret the transition to sustainability, whether reactively (based on legal compliance) or proactively (based on radical experimentation).	The research is limited to the plastic packaging industry and a specific geographical context. Generalizing the findings to other industries and contexts may be limited.

By analyzing various in-depth case studies and empirical research, this article aims to provide insights into how incumbent firms can successfully navigate the challenges and opportunities associated with sustainability, contributing to the development of more environmentally and socially responsible business models.

2. Landasan Teori

- **Corporate Governance**

Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is a system that regulates and controls a company. GCG aims to balance the rights of stakeholders, ensuring transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, and fairness in corporate management (Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu George, 2007). Effective GCG mechanisms can improve company performance, reduce risk, and attract investors (Aras & Crowther, 2008; Chabachib et al., 2020; Diamastuti et al., 2021).

- **Sustainability**

Corporate sustainability involves managing the environmental and social impacts of business operations, in addition to financial performance (Jamali et al., 2008). This includes practices such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, social responsibility, and sustainability reporting. Sustainable companies focus not only on short-term profits but also on long-term impacts on the environment and society.

- **Firm Performance**

Firm performance can be measured across various dimensions, including financial performance (e.g., profitability, growth), social performance (e.g., impact on society), and environmental performance (e.g., carbon footprint). Good CG and sustainability practices have been shown to have a positive impact on overall firm performance (Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu George, 2007; Chabachib et al., 2020; Diamastuti et al., 2021; Yahaya & Musa, 2023).

- **Multi-Level Perspective**

To fully understand the relationship between CG, sustainability, and firm performance, it is crucial to adopt a multi-level perspective. This perspective recognizes that factors at the individual (e.g., entrepreneurial orientation), organizational (e.g., board structure), and ecosystem (e.g., stakeholder engagement) levels all play a role in shaping a company's sustainability performance (Aras & Crowther, 2008; Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu George, 2007).

- **Proactive vs. Reactive Dynamics**

Incumbent firms can approach sustainability transitions either proactively, by leading in the adoption of new practices, or reactively, by responding to external pressures. The discussion will explore how these dynamics affect the effectiveness of the transition towards a more sustainable business model (Zucchella et al., 2022).

- **Institutional Influence**

Government regulations, industry norms, and social pressures can all shape a company's CG and sustainability practices. The discussion will analyze how these institutional influences vary across countries and industries, and how they impact firm performance (Aras & Crowther, 2008; Diamastuti et al., 2021).

- **Circular Business Model Innovation**

Circular business models, which focus on waste reduction, reuse, and recycling, are a key concept in the transition towards sustainability. The article will investigate how incumbent firms, particularly in the plastic packaging industry, can develop and implement effective circular business models (Zucchella et al., 2022).

- **Stakeholder Engagement**

Stakeholder engagement, including customers, suppliers, governments, and local communities, can be either a driver or a barrier to sustainability transitions. This article will examine the role of stakeholder engagement in shaping sustainability practices and firm performance (Jamali et al., 2008).

3. Discussion

a. Corporate Governance and Sustainability

GCG and Sustainability are two concepts that are increasingly intertwined in the contemporary business landscape. GCG, which encompasses principles such as transparency, accountability, and responsibility, has long been recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing corporate performance. Prior research has demonstrated that effective GCG can improve financial performance, mitigate risks, and enhance investor confidence (Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu

George, 2007). However, in recent years, the focus of GCG has expanded beyond mere financial considerations to include the environmental and social dimensions of business operations. This is reflected in the growing emphasis on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices.

Jamali et al. (2008), in their research in Lebanon, found that good GCG is a necessary foundation for sustainable CSR. Companies with strong GCG structures tend to be more mindful of the social and environmental impacts of their activities. Additionally, Diamastuti et al.'s (2021) research in Indonesia highlights the important role of the government in promoting CSR disclosure through regulations and policies. These findings suggest that GCG and CSR are mutually reinforcing, where effective GCG can facilitate better CSR practices, and in turn, good CSR practices can enhance a company's reputation and contribute to long-term performance.

b. Firm Performance, Sustainability, and Business Model Innovation

The relationship between GCG, sustainability, and firm performance is complex and multifaceted. Research has shown that good GCG and sustainability practices can enhance a company's financial performance (Cătălin Mihail & Claudiu George, 2007; Chabachib et al., 2020). However, this relationship is not always straightforward and can be influenced by various factors. Yahaya & Musa (2023) found that some GCG mechanisms, such as board size, may not always have a significant impact on firm value. This suggests that the effectiveness of GCG mechanisms can vary depending on the company and industry context.

Furthermore, Zucchella et al.'s (2021) research indicates that business model innovation, particularly circular business models that focus on waste reduction, reuse, and recycling, can be key in improving a company's sustainability performance. Companies that proactively embrace innovation and experimentation tend to be more successful in transitioning towards more sustainable business models.

c. Multi-Level Perspective and Institutional Influence

It is essential to understand the relationship between GCG, sustainability, and firm performance from a multi-level perspective. Factors at the individual (e.g., entrepreneurial orientation), organizational (e.g., board structure), and ecosystem (e.g., stakeholder engagement) levels all play a role in shaping a company's sustainability performance. At the individual level, entrepreneurial orientation, characterized by proactivity, innovation, and risk-taking, has been shown to be a significant driver in the transition towards sustainability (Zucchella et al., 2022). At the organizational level, board structure, managerial ownership, and organizational commitment to sustainability can influence CSR practices and firm performance (Chabachib et al., 2020; Diamastuti et al., 2021). At the ecosystem level, stakeholder engagement and institutional influences, such as government regulations and industry norms, can shape a company's sustainability practices (Aras & Crowther, 2008; Yahaya & Musa, 2023).

d. Proactive vs. Reactive Dynamics and Stakeholder Engagement

Incumbent firms can approach sustainability transitions in two ways: proactively or reactively. Proactive companies take the lead in adopting new practices and innovating to reduce their environmental and social impacts. In contrast, reactive companies tend to respond to external pressures, such as government regulations or consumer demands, rather than voluntarily implementing sustainability practices.

Zucchella et al.'s (2021) research suggests that a proactive approach to sustainability transitions tends to be more effective. Companies that actively seek ways to reduce waste, reuse materials, and recycle their products are more likely to succeed in achieving their sustainability goals. Stakeholder engagement is also a crucial factor in driving sustainability transitions. Companies that actively involve their stakeholders in the decision-making process tend to be more successful in implementing sustainability practices (Jamali et al., 2008).

In conclusion, the relationship between corporate governance, sustainability, and firm performance is complex and dynamic. The discussion has shown that good GCG, sustainability practices, and circular business model innovation can enhance overall firm performance. However, the effectiveness of these factors can vary depending on the company context, industry, and country. Future research can continue to delve into this complex relationship, focusing on how incumbent firms can successfully navigate the challenges and opportunities associated with sustainability. Further research can also investigate how institutional influences and stakeholder engagement can shape sustainability practices and firm performance.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

a. Conclusions

Research on GCG, sustainability, and firm performance has provided valuable insights into how established firms can navigate the evolving business landscape. Effective GCG, encompassing transparency, accountability, and responsibility, has proven to be a crucial foundation for corporate sustainability practices. Managerial ownership, independent boards of commissioners, and appropriate board sizes can enhance firm performance, while excessive institutional ownership can pose challenges.

Furthermore, this discussion emphasizes the government's essential role in shaping GCG and sustainability practices through regulations and policies. Organizational commitment to sustainability is also a key factor in driving CSR disclosures and overall firm performance. Transitioning towards circular business models, especially in industries with high environmental impacts like plastic packaging, presents a significant challenge for established firms. However, this research indicates that proactive approaches to sustainability, supported by entrepreneurial leadership and strategic experimentation, can yield positive outcomes.

b. Recommendations

Based on the discussion in this article, the following recommendations are proposed:

- For firms: Established firms should proactively embrace sustainability practices and effective GCG. This can be achieved through the development and implementation of circular business models, active stakeholder engagement, and transparent CSR disclosures.
- For the government: The government should continue to play an active role in shaping and enforcing regulations that promote good GCG and sustainability practices. Incentives and support can be provided to firms that demonstrate a commitment to sustainability.
- For investors: Investors should consider GCG and sustainability factors in their investment decisions. Firms with good GCG and sustainability practices tend to have better long-term performance and lower risk.

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